

**The role of digital skills in the employability of young graduates:
The case of a company responsible for delegated management of public
services in Morocco.**

**Le rôle des compétences numériques dans l'employabilité des jeunes
diplômés : Le cas d'une entreprise chargée de la gestion déléguée des
services publics au Maroc.**

MABROUKI El Mostafa

PhD student - Researcher
Laboratory of Economics and Management of Organizations
University of Ibn Tofail – Kenitra, Morocco

KHATORI Youssef

Professor - Researcher
Laboratory of Economics and Management of Organizations
University of Ibn Tofail – Kenitra, Morocco

TOURI Firdaouss Hibat Allah

PhD student - Researcher
Laboratory of Economics and Management of Organizations
University of Ibn Tofail – Kenitra, Morocco

ACHOUR Fatima Zahra

Professor - Researcher
Laboratory of Economics and Management of Organizations
University of Ibn Tofail – Kenitra, Morocco

Date de soumission : 22/11/2023

Date d'acceptation : 04/01/2024

Pour citer cet article :

MABROUKI.E & AL (2024) «The role of digital skills in the employability of young graduates: The case of a company responsible for delegated management of public services in Morocco», Revue Française d'Économie et de Gestion «Volume 5 : Numéro 1 » pp : 319 – 338.

Author(s) agree that this article remain permanently open access under the terms of the Creative Commons

Attribution License 4.0 International License

Abstract

Our study aims to highlight the role of digital skills in the employability of young graduates in the professional context of delegated management of public services in Morocco, regarding the theoretical approaches developed in this framework. Through a qualitative study, we will present initial results relating to the context of the study, while targeting young people recruited within the company studied with a view to confirming and enriching the existing conceptual framework.

In addition, the results show that the academic training provided by Moroccan universities/higher education establishments does not correspond perfectly to the needs of companies, particularly in the field of digitalization. Furthermore, self-training and continuing education play a sine qua non role in filling the skills gap for graduates.

Keywords: digital skills; employability; management of public services

Résumé

Notre étude vise à mettre en évidence le rôle des compétences digitales dans l'employabilité des jeunes diplômés dans le contexte professionnel de la gestion déléguée des services publics au Maroc, au regard des approches théoriques développées dans ce cadre. A travers une étude qualitative, nous présenterons les premiers résultats relatifs au contexte de l'étude, tout en ciblant les jeunes recrutés au sein de l'entreprise étudiée en vue de confirmer et d'enrichir le cadre conceptuel existant.

Par ailleurs, les résultats montrent que la formation académique dispensée par les universités/établissements d'enseignement supérieur marocains ne correspond pas parfaitement aux besoins des entreprises, notamment dans le domaine de la digitalisation. En outre, l'autoformation et la formation continue jouent un rôle sine qua non pour combler le déficit de compétences des diplômés.

Mots-clés : compétences digitales ; employabilité ; gestion des services publics

Introduction

The digital revolution has changed the way businesses operate and interact with their environment, and the COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated this dynamic. Virtually all organizations are now adopting new digital technologies to improve productivity, reduce costs, expand their presence, and adapt to the needs of their customers. (Gebayew et al., 2028). Digital tools such as online collaboration platforms, virtual communication tools, mobile applications, social networks, etc. are now part of every company's strategy. In this context, digital skills play a crucial role in the success of a digital transformation strategy. (Cetindamar et al., 2021).

In this context, young graduates need to be able to align themselves quickly with the needs of the market and master some of the digital skills needed to succeed in their field.

Digital skills are now a real lever for working in almost every industry, whether in healthcare, education, commerce, finance, communications, marketing, or even public service management. (Frey, C. & M. Osborne, 2013, McKinsey Global Institute (MGI), 2017).

Indeed, companies are increasingly looking to recruit people who are proficient in the use of digital tools, who are able to work collaboratively from a distance, to explore the usefulness of social networks, who can rapidly analyze data to make decisions (Big Data), who develop innovative projects and who are able to solve problems effectively and efficiently. (Acemoglu, D. & Autor, D., 2011, Petropoulos, G., 2018).

The candidates who have these skills tend to have a competitive advantage compared to those who do not (Almeida et al., 2018, Kee, et al., 2023), therefore, they can easily adapt to new technologies and changes in the labor market and can contribute to the growth and innovation of the company.

In addition, employers are looking to hire candidates who can bring an innovative perspective to the business. However, "digital skills" are still evolving and are poorly defined in the literature, which can lead to gaps between the skills acquired, developed in particular during their academic career, and the requirements of companies, which are constantly evolving.

Our objective in this paper is to study the role of young graduates' digital skills in their employability on the labor market in the Moroccan professional context.

Our research question is as follows: In which way do digital skills influence the employability of young graduates in the context of delegated management of public services in Morocco?

This study will enable us to better understand how the acquisition of digital skills directly impacts the competitiveness of young graduates in the public service market.

In addition, this research offers the opportunity to identify the specific needs of the Moroccan labor market in terms of digital skills, which can guide higher education institutions in adapting their training programs to better prepare students for their future careers. It will also enable us to explore possible disparities between the skills on offer from young graduates and the expectations of employers, particularly in the context of public service management.

For this purpose, we will begin with a review of the literature, mentioning the main studies that have addressed the subject and presenting our research model, developed on the basis of the literature review. We will then present the research methodology adopted (case study), examine the research results and discuss them, and end with a conclusion in which we will indicate the implications and prospects of the study.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1. DIGITAL SKILLS

In the last few years, the issue of digital skills (also known as digital competencies) has become of increasing concern to researchers and professionals, due to the growing use of digital technologies in the daily life of organizations. Some definitions of "digital skills" generally include criteria such as the use of digital technologies for communication, virtual collaboration, information retrieval, problem solving, creativity, online security, data management and critical thinking regarding their use. (Almeida et al., 2018, Kee, et al., 2023).

In the same vein, Pettersson points out that digital competence is the ability to use information and communication technologies (ICT) effectively and responsibly to solve problems, communicate and carry out tasks. (Pettersson, 2018).

Several research studies have shown that digital skills have become an essential element for professional success. Candidates with high digital skills tend to have a competitive advantage on the job market (Autor et al. 2003).

The subject was also studied from another social dimension, highlighting the impact of digital inequality, which can lead to social and economic exclusion for people who do not have access to digital skills and technologies. These inequalities can be expressed in terms of gaps in access to these technologies, as well as the level of mastery of their use between different social groups, such as young and old, men and women, urban and rural populations, developed and underdeveloped countries (Drori, G. S., & Jang, Y. S., 2003, McKinsey Global Institute (MGI), 2017). The effects of such a situation of inequality can have negative repercussions on several social dimensions of the populations concerned, such as the difficulty of finding a job and succeeding in a professional career, accessing online services, communicating with others, and

benefiting from a more democratic life. (Foust, C. R., & Hoyt, K. D., 2018). It can also lead to a lack of confidence in the use of technology and digital exclusion. (Hargittai, E., 2003). Hargittai points out that digital inequality can be an obstacle to equal opportunities, as well as to the country's economic competitiveness, due in particular to inequalities in terms of Internet access and the lack of digital skills. She also noted that digital inequality is a complex phenomenon that can be influenced by many factors, such as age, level of education, income, place of residence and ethnicity. (Lyons, et al. 2019).

Furthermore, digital inequalities can contribute to the degradation of existing socio-economic inequalities due to a lack of access to digital technologies and digital skills, which can affect the quality of their access to information, education, and employment. (Hargittai, E., 2003).

The context of the COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the disparities in access to technologies and digital skills. However, digital transformation is a complex and dynamic process that requires a considered and strategic approach, based on increased collaboration between stakeholders, including governments, universities, teachers, and students, to meet the challenges and exploit the opportunities it offers. (Mhlanga, D., & Moloi, T., 2020).

1.2. EMPLOYABILITY IN THE DIGITAL AGE

Employability is the extent to which an individual can acquire and maintain gainful, fulfilling employment that is consistent with his or her personal skills, interests, and values, while being able to adapt to changes in the labor market. (Behle, H., 2020, Kee et al., 2023). According to Hillage and Pollard (1999), employability refers to an individual's ability to:

- Obtaining an initial job, which is determined mainly by the education system.
- Maintaining a job and moving between different jobs and roles within the same organization.
- Finding a new job if necessary.

These researchers focused on three fundamental aspects of the concept of employability: skills, job stability and adaptability. Skills encompass the technical and non-technical knowledge and abilities needed to do a job, job stability concerns job security and the ability to opt for a transition in the labor market, while adaptability refers to an individual's ability to adapt to changes and evolve in their professional career. This analytical framework has been largely used by researchers and decision-makers to guide employability policies and to help individuals develop the skills and aptitudes they need to succeed in the labor market. (Hillage and Pollard, 1999).

In fact, technological advances have influenced organizations' need for qualified profiles with skills related to the digital ecosystem. (Autor et al. 2003, Almeida et al., 2018). As a result, young graduates who do not have these skills may find it difficult to find or keep their first job. In this context, academic training and/or continuing training within the company can help to improve the employability of employees. (Acemoglu, D., & Autor, D., 2011).

Other researchers such as Georg Graetz and Guy Michaels, (2015) have shown that lower-skilled employees are the most negatively affected by robotization, as their work is often focused on repetitive tasks that can be easily automated. However, skilled employees tend to work more easily with more complex machines that are more difficult to automate, which can increase their productivity and improve their employability. (Graetz, G. & G. Michaels, 2015). These researchers also found that the use of robots had a negative effect on the salaries of less qualified employees and a positive effect on the evolution of the salaries of more qualified employees in terms of digital skills. (Autor et al. 2003).

In the context of artificial intelligence and the automation of tasks, the employability of young graduates is based on several criteria, including the need to have prerequisites in IT, as well as problem-solving skills. (Goos, M. & Manning, A., 2007). Young graduates need a variety of skills to succeed in the modern job market, including the ability to learn new technologies, to adapt to a constantly changing environment and to be flexible. In addition, they must have communication and virtual collaboration skills, as well as an aptitude for creativity and innovation to find new solutions and work autonomously, while being able to manage their time effectively. Finally, it could be said that young graduates have an obligation to develop skills and knowledge in digital technologies to facilitate their integration into the labor market. However, this does not necessarily guarantee their employability, as other factors, such as soft skills, can also play a complementary role.

❖ WHAT ROLE DOES ACADEMIC EDUCATION PLAY?

Academic education plays a crucial role in the development of digital skills among young graduates. In theory, it provides them with the knowledge and skills they need to use digital technologies effectively and creatively. (Kee et al., 2023).

During their studies, students are required to master certain basic subjects linked to the digitalization of organizational processes, such as data analysis, cybersecurity, and information technology. The students must also familiarize themselves with emerging technologies and learn how to use them effectively in a professional context. In addition, it is essential to put their theoretical knowledge into practice, through work placements, group projects and in-

company research projects that involve the use of digital technologies. These practical activities can give students hands-on experience of how to use these technologies in a professional context, preparing them for a future in which these skills are increasingly required (Kee et al., 2023).

With this perspective, digital immersion can enable students to interact with virtual environments using technologies such as virtual or augmented reality, e-learning, and the use of digital tools by teachers in their teaching approaches, which can contribute to the development of their digital skills. (Ramírez-Montoya, M.S. et al., 2022).

By giving learners the opportunity to immerse themselves in simulated environments, digital immersion can enable students to acquire practical skills in problem-solving, virtual collaboration and critical thinking. (Bonfils, P., 2015, Ramírez-Montoya, M.S. et al., 2022).

Indeed, the quality of academic education can influence students' perceived employability, insofar as teachers can provide students with the relevant information and knowledge to better understand the expectations of the labor market and develop appropriate professional skills. (Petruzzello et al., 2023, Ramírez-Montoya et al., 2022).

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To conduct this study, we adopted a qualitative research methodology based on a case study (the case of Redal), with the aim of gaining an in-depth understanding of the role of digital skills in the employability of young graduates in the Moroccan professional context, focusing on the sector of delegated management of public services. order of this, we collected data from 5 new recruits, using semi-structured interviews as our data collection method. This approach enabled us to ask open-ended questions based on our interview guide (see Table 1). After collecting the data, we carried out a thematic analysis of its content. This enabled us to understand the role of the acquisition of digital skills among young graduates in their employability, as well as some implications for practice and research in this field.

The employees interviewed were selected based on their seniority within the company:

Interviewee 1: Hydraulic Engineer, 2.4 years of seniority.

Interviewee 2: Customer Executive, 10 months' seniority.

Interviewee 3: Drinking Water Project Manager, 5 months' seniority.

Interviewee 4: Electrical Engineer, one year's seniority.

Interviewee 5: Customer executive, 1.5 years' seniority,

Interviewee 6: Head of Recruitment (HR), (15 years' seniority)

Interviewee 7: Local HR manager (27 years' seniority)

Tableau N°1 : Interview grid for the study

Main axes	sub-themes
Digital skills and employability in the Moroccan professional context.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The relationship between digital skills and the employability of young graduates. - The coherence between academic achievements and company requirements in terms of digital skills. - The influence of emerging digital trends (for example: virtual collaborative working, social networks, artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, etc.).
Role of academic and continuing training.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the key digital skills that young graduates need to succeed in the job market? - Adapting academic education programs to the requirements of the labor market. - The role of continuing education in improving the employability of young people

Source: Established by the authors

2.1. The case studied:

Redal is a subsidiary of the French multinational Veolia Environment Maroc, which manages the distribution of water, electricity, and liquid wastewater treatment for more than 2.2 million citizens in 23 communes and districts of Rabat, Sale, Temara, Skhirat, Bouznika and Charrat, under a delegated management contract (According to Dahir n° 1-06-15 of 15 moharrem 1427 (14 February 2006), which promulgates law n° 54-05 relating to the delegated management of public services, the latter is defined as a contract in which a legal entity under public law, called the "delegator temporarily entrusts the management of a public service for which it is responsible to a legal entity governed by public or private law, called the "delegatee", while granting it the right to collect a fee from users and/or to make a profit from the said management (article 2, law no. 54-05).

The company has around 1,700 employees, over 27% of whom are women, and a management ratio of around 21%.

Since 2019, Redal has launched a digital transformation strategy, aimed primarily at improving customer service, simplifying processes, and optimizing operations. Structural actions have been put in place with this in mind, including the use of mobile applications, internal websites, and official pages on social networks to enable customers to opt for e-invoicing, e-payment, e-claims, and e-branching. In terms of internal processes, the digital strategy aims to simplify professional channels and adapt services to the needs of employees.

3. Analysis of results

In this section, we present the key findings from the analysis of each theme included in our interview guide.

3.1. Method of analysis

To obtain a representation of the concepts studied, we opted for a thematic analysis.

The aim of thematic analysis is to discover and describe the main themes or topics that emerge from the qualitative data collected, in order to better understand the underlying content and meanings.

Tableau N°2 : Themes raised in interviews 6 and 7

Themes	Description
Digital transformation as a business strategy	Companies see digital transformation as a strategic challenge. It enables them to optimize resources, improve process efficiency, strengthen customer relations and prevent cyber security threats. Digital knowledge and skills have become essential to meeting market expectations and maintaining competitiveness.
The need for digital skills	Companies are actively looking for talent capable of adapting and thriving in a constantly changing environment marked by digital transformation. Digital skills are seen as an important competitive advantage and a key criterion in the recruitment process.
The importance of digital skills in public service management	Digital skills are relevant in the water distribution, electricity, and various liquid waste treatment sectors. Candidates who master digital technologies can improve the customer experience, develop innovative solutions, optimize management processes and ensure infrastructure efficiency.
Education and development of digital skills	The company has opted for ongoing education programs to develop the digital skills of its human capital. These courses focus on the digitalization of customer relations practices and virtual collaborative working. They are designed to be interactive and practical, encouraging the active involvement of employees.
A culture of continuous learning	Companies encourage a culture of continuous learning, where employees are encouraged to develop and update their digital skills. This enables them to maintain a skilled workforce that is adapted to the company's needs in a constantly evolving digital environment.

Source : Established by the authors

Tableau N°3 : Themes raised in interviews 6 and 7

Themes	Description
Mastery of digital transformation concepts	According to the five interviewees, mastery of the fundamental concepts of the digital transformation of businesses is essential for landing a first job and facilitating professional integration. Recruiters attach great importance to these skills during job interviews.
The use of digital tools and platforms	The digital skills involve mastering specific digital tools and platforms. The interviews highlighted the use of tools such as Google's G Suite, professional social networks such as LinkedIn, as well as analyzing data and solving customer-related problems using digital technologies.
Self-study	The interviewees stressed the importance of self-training in the development of digital skills. Self-study offers flexibility, autonomy and access to a variety of online resources for acquiring new skills and keeping up to date with technological advances.
Developing transversal skills	In addition to technical skills, self-study also enables the development of transversal skills such as problem-solving, time management, finding relevant information and the ability to learn independently. These skills are considered essential in a constantly changing working environment.
Adaptation to a new corporate culture	Digital transformation is driving cultural change within organizations. Employees have to adapt to new collaborative working practices, online communication and the use of digital tools. Digital skills help them to integrate quickly and effectively into this environment.
Revision of pedagogical programs	Interviewees highlighted the lack of education in digital skills during their time at university. They suggest that pedagogical programs need to be revised to include courses focusing on emerging technologies, digital skills, online project management and virtual collaboration.

Source : Established by the authors

This thematic analysis of the data collected shows the importance of digital skills in the employability of young graduates. Skills linked to digital transformation are sought after by employers and enable individuals to adapt to the demands of the labor market. Self-study and the revision of university curricula are proposed as ways of improving the acquisition of these skills and encouraging a successful transition to an increasingly digital professional environment.

Equally, mastery of the fundamental concepts of the digital transformation of businesses is seen as essential for landing a first job, facilitating professional integration, and promoting career development. The comments of the various interviewees highlight the importance of mastering digital skills and new approaches to work linked to digitalization.

It is interesting to note that several interviewees also highlighted a lack of education in the field of digital transformation during their university career. They therefore suggest a review of pedagogical programs to better prepare students for the demands of the constantly evolving labor market.

3.2. Discussion of results

The results of this study highlight the crucial importance of digital skills in the context of delegated management of public services in Morocco. The interviews conducted highlight the transition towards a digital culture in the Moroccan professional world, where information and communication technology skills have become an essential requirement for the employability of young graduates.

As far as training is concerned, the study shows that the acquisition of digital skills during academic training is a decisive factor in the employability of young graduates. However, gaps are identified in university curricula, underlining the need to adapt them to the needs of the job market, by including courses on emerging technologies, digital skills, online project management and virtual collaboration.

3.2.1 Digital skills and employability of young graduates in the context of delegated management of public services:

Our objective in this section is to get a true picture of the role of young graduates' digital skills in terms of their employability in the context of companies responsible for the delegated management of public services in Morocco.

❖ The issues of digital skills in the Moroccan professional context:

Our interviews revealed that digital skills have become increasingly important in the professional world in Morocco. Employers are increasingly looking for young graduates with a digital mindset, as well as skills in information and communication technologies, because these skills are seen as an asset in a world that is constantly evolving digitally. Employers are looking for skills such as proficiency in IT tools, collaborative working, remote project management, e-learning, cyber-security and digital marketing.

Digital knowledge and skills have become essential for the employability of young graduates. The digital transformation strategy launched by our company in 2019 has reinforced this need for digital skills» (Interviewee 7).

« The digital skills of candidates are an important competitive asset and help determine their success in relation to other candidates. (...) the various professions related to the management of public services, place great importance on the digital skills of candidates". (Interviewee 6).

The context of delegated management of public services involves the collection, storage and analysis of large quantities of data in real time, requiring advanced digital skills to make effective and efficient use of the technologies available.

« For the job of hydraulic engineer, digital devices now play an important role in the efficient management of the whole activity, such as collecting and analyzing hydraulic data to improve project performance, communicating with customers and partners on digital platforms and supervising field operations remotely. As a result, mastery of these new approaches to work is crucial to employability"» (Interviewee 1).

Moreover, young graduates with digital skills are also able to contribute to innovation and the continuous improvement of their business processes. They can propose innovative technological solutions to resolve the problems and challenges faced by companies in this sector, such as optimizing resource management, reducing costs, improving service quality and protecting the environment.

« As an electrical engineer, access to the job market means being well prepared to work with new technologies, not only in terms of electricity operation and maintenance, but also in terms of team management and internal and external communication with stakeholders. In this context, the use of these technologies can bring significant added value in terms of employability, and involves mastery of certain skills, for example:

- *Predictive maintenance: Internet of Things (IoT) technologies make it possible to monitor the performance of power grid equipment in real time and identify problems before they occur. This improves network reliability and reduces maintenance costs.*
- *Automation: automated control systems used to monitor and control power system equipment, minimizing downtime and maximizing efficiency (telecontrol, hub grade).*
- *Real-time communication: Real-time communication systems make it possible to react quickly to breakdowns or problems. This improves customer satisfaction and service quality. » (Interviewee 4).*

In fact, digital skills have become a major asset for young graduates looking to break into this sector. These skills enable them to better understand and master the information and communication technologies used, to propose innovative solutions, and to be better prepared to meet constantly changing professional requirements.

Following this line of thinking, Morocco is facing a shortage of qualified professionals in the field of information and communication technologies. In this context, the Moroccan government has put in place several initiatives to encourage the development of digital skills, notably through the Plan Maroc Numeric 2020, which aims to make Morocco a regional hub for information and communication technologies.

❖ **The role of critical thinking and content creation:**

The thematic analysis of the content collected through our various interviews shows that the professional world has become increasingly connected. This implies that employees are aware of the corporate image they project on social networks and in their interactions with the outside world. Indeed, employee actions such as writing statuses on social networks, sharing images, producing videos, creating infographics, etc., can have a significant impact on the company's reputation (the company's digital ambassadors). So, mastery of communication techniques is essential for communicating effectively with stakeholders such as customers, partners and suppliers. (Acemoglu, D. & Autor, D., 2011, Petropoulos, G., 2018, Almeida et al., 2018).

In this context, cyber-security has become a major challenge for companies. Employees need to be trained in the basic principles of cyber security, such as preventing phishing, social engineering and scams, in order to avert the risks associated with the use of these technologies. Regulatory provisions must also be considered to avoid data breaches and the associated penalties. Ongoing training can play a crucial role in transferring these skills to employees, particularly young recruits.

On the other hand, digitalization brings with it a host of new technologies and tools that can be used to improve business processes. However, these technologies can also have negative impacts on privacy, data security and the environment. Indeed, it's important for young recruits to think critically about the benefits and risks associated with using these technologies.

They need to be able to ask the right questions, verify sources of information and analyze data to make informed decisions. They must also be aware of the ethical and environmental issues associated with the use of new technologies.

The critical thinking skills of young recruits can also help stimulate innovation and creativity within the company, by challenging existing processes and proposing new ideas and approaches.

This can support the company's ability to remain competitive in the marketplace and adapt to technological and societal change.

3.3. The role of academic and continuing education in developing digital skills:

In this section, we present the role of academic and continuing education in the development of digital skills. Indeed, the content analysis of our interviews revealed that these skills have become a major issue for the employability of young graduates in the labor market.

3.3.1. The role of academic training

Our interviews reveal that the acquisition of digital skills through academic education has a significant impact on the perceived employability of young graduates. Indeed, as confirmed by the researchers' study Kee, et al. (2023), Acemoglu, D., & Autor, D. (2011), Ramírez-Montoya, M.S. et al., (2022), courses, practical workshops, internships, and research projects give students the opportunity to acquire the specific technical and practical skills they need to make effective use of digital technologies in their field of activity.

These digital skills acquired during academic training are of great use to young graduates when they enter the job market. Employers are increasingly looking for candidates who possess these digital skills, as they are seen as an asset in a professional world that is constantly evolving digitally.

The young recruits interviewed indicated that during the COVID-19 pandemic, their academic education courses were mostly organized remotely, through tools such as videoconferencing, email, and social networks. This situation led to immersion in the virtual world, and enabled them to develop new skills, such as mastery of these tools and the ability to communicate effectively at a distance. They were thus able to adapt to this new way of working, and had to learn to organize their time independently, stay focused despite potential distractions, and manage their home working environment.

All this has helped to develop a digital culture among students, which can be useful in their future professional lives and for their employability. However, we have noticed that university programs need to adapt to the needs of the job market, particularly in terms of new communication and information technologies. *« Being equipped with tools and skills linked to the digitization of organizations is essential for developing one's professional career. However, during my time at university, I noticed a lack of training in this area. In*

my opinion, educational programs need to be revised to be more compatible and appropriate to the requirements and developments of the job market. Universities should include courses on emerging technologies, digital skills, online project management and virtual collaboration. In this way, young graduates would be better prepared to meet employers' expectations and adapt more easily to changes in the world of work. » (Interviewee 3).

3.3.2. The role of continuing education:

In addition, analysis of our interviews shows that ongoing training enables new recruits to keep up to date with the latest technologies and practices in their field, and to acquire specialized skills to meet the demands of their jobs.

« When I joined Redal, I took part in an ongoing training course on digitalization as part of a project called SATAWAD (Secure Any Time, Anywhere, Any Device, Any Content), during which I was able to immerse myself in the company's new digitalization culture.

This involved mastering the "G-suite" package, which is a suite of online productivity tools offered by Google for collaborative working. It comprises a range of tools such as Google Docs, Sheets, Slides and Drive, which enable you to work on documents in real time, collaborate remotely, share files and information, and communicate easily with colleagues, etc. » (Interviewee 5).

What's more, young graduates are required to learn new skills throughout their professional careers, as technology is constantly evolving. Ongoing education programs and self-study can help them acquire these skills and remain competitive in the job market.

« By investing in the development of our staff's digital skills, we are positioning ourselves favorably in a world where digitalization has become unavoidable.» (Interviewee 7).

Figure N°1 : Summary of the relationship between digital skills and graduate employability

Source: Prepared by the authors

Conclusion

The digital transformation of companies in the Moroccan context has favored the decisive role of digital skills for the employability of young graduates, particularly in the context of delegated management of public services.

Indeed, in-company training remains the essential source for filling the digital skills gap among new recruits. Universities and colleges must take this dimension into account in their training courses. Some of the perspectives of this research are as follows:

- Study of this theme in relation to salary trends, internal promotion, the acquisition of positions of responsibility, and in the public and private sectors.
- Quantitative studies to reach different contexts and populations, enabling study results to be generalized.

It should be pointed out that the results of our current research study cannot be generalized (case study) but are intended to highlight the specificities of the context in the first instance, likely to enrich the conceptual framework addressed.

Our qualitative research is limited to the context of the study. However, it will contribute to highlighting the existing gap between the new graduates and the company's need for skills through the delegated management of public services.

BIBLIOGRAPHIE

- **Frey, C.** & Osborne, M. (2013), *The Future of Employment: How Susceptible Are Jobs To Computerisation?*, Oxford: Oxford Martin School,
- **McKinsey.** & Company MGI (2017), *A Future that Works: Automation, Employment, and Productivity*, McKinsey Global Institute.
- **Petropoulos, G.** (2018). The impact of artificial intelligence on employment. *Praise for Work in the Digital Age*, 119, 121.
- **Kee, D. M. H.** & Anwar, A., Gwee, S. L., & Ijaz, M. F. (2023). Impact of Acquisition of Digital Skills on Perceived Employability of Youth: Mediating Role of Course Quality. *Information*, 14(1), 42.
- **Pettersson, F.** (2018). On the issues of digital competence in educational contexts—a review of literature. *Education and information technologies*, 23(3), 1005-1021.
- **Drori, G. S.** & Jang, Y. S. (2003). The global digital divide: A sociological assessment of trends and causes. *Social science computer review*, 21(2), 144-161.
- **Foust, C. R.** & Hoyt, K. D. (2018). Social movement 2.0: Integrating and assessing scholarship on social media and movement. *Review of Communication*, 18(1), 37-55.

- **Hargittai, E.** (2003). The digital divide and what to do about it. New economy handbook, 2003, 821-839.
- **Lyons, A. & Zucchetti C. & Kass-Hanna, A. & Cobo, J.C.** (2019). Bridging the gap between digital skills and employability for vulnerable populations. IN THE DIGITAL AGE.
- **Behle, H.** (2020). Students' and graduates' employability. A framework to classify and measure employability gain. Policy reviews in higher education, 4(1), 105-130.
- **Hillage, J. & Pollard, E.** (1998). Employability: developing a framework for policy analysis.
- **Almeida, R. & Leite Corseuil, C. H. & Poole, J.** (2018). The impact of digital technologies on worker tasks: Do labor policies matter?.
- **Autor, D. H. & Levy, F. & Murnane, R. J.** (2003). The skill content of recent technological change: An empirical exploration. The Quarterly journal of economics, 118(4), 1279-1333.
- **Acemoglu, D. & Autor, D.** (2011). Skills, tasks and technologies: Implications for employment and earnings. In Handbook of labor economics (Vol. 4, pp. 1043-1171). Elsevier.
- **Graetz, G. & Michaels, G.** (2015), 'Robots at Work', CEPS Discussion Paper 1335, London: London School of Economics, <http://cep.lse.ac.uk/pubs/download/dp1335.pdf>.
- **Goos, M. & Manning, A.** (2007). Lousy and lovely jobs: The rising polarization of work in Britain. The review of economics and statistics, 89(1), 118-133.
- **Ramírez-Montoya, M. S. & Castillo-Martínez, I. M. & Sanabria-Z, J. & Miranda, J.** (2022). Complex thinking in the framework of Education 4.0 and Open Innovation—A systematic literature review. Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity, 8(1), 4.
- **Bonfils, P.** (2015). Immersion et environnements numériques: une approche méthodologique par l'expérience vécue. Questions de communication, (27), 261-277.
- **Petruzzello, G. & Mariani, M. G., Guglielmi, D., van der Heijden, B. I., de Jong, J. P., & Chiesa, R.** (2023). The role of teaching staff in fostering perceived employability of university students. Studies in Higher Education, 48(1), 20-36.
- **González-Pérez, L. I. & Ramírez-Montoya, M. S.** (2022). Components of Education 4.0 in 21st century skills frameworks: systematic review. Sustainability, 14(3), 1493.

- **Gebayew, C. & Hardini, I. R. & Panjaitan, G. H. A. & Kurniawan, N. B.** (2018). A systematic literature review on digital transformation. In 2018 International Conference on Information Technology Systems and Innovation (ICITSI) (pp. 260-265). IEEE.
- **Cetindamar Kozanoglu, D. & Abedin, B.** (2021). Understanding the role of employees in digital transformation: conceptualization of digital literacy of employees as a multi-dimensional organizational affordance. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 34(6), 1649-1672.
- **McKinsey Global Institute (MGI)** (2017), *A Future that Works: Automation, Employment, and Productivity*, McKinsey & Company.
- **Petropoulos, G.** (2018). The impact of artificial intelligence on employment. *Praise for Work in the Digital Age*, 119, 121.
- **Petterson, F.** (2018). On the issues of digital competence in educational contexts—a review of literature. *Education and information technologies*, 23(3), 1005-1021.
- **G. S. & Jang, Y. S.** (2003). The global digital divide: A sociological assessment of trends and causes. *Social science computer review*, 21(2), 144-161.
- **Hargittai, E.** (2003). The digital divide and what to do about it. *New economy handbook*, 2003, 821-839.
- **Lyons, A. C. & Zucchetti, A., Kass-Hanna, J., & Cobo, C.** (2019). Bridging the gap between digital skills and employability for vulnerable populations. *IN THE DIGITAL AGE*.
- **Behle, H.** (2020). Students' and graduates' employability. A framework to classify and measure employability gain. *Policy reviews in higher education*, 4(1), 105-130.
- **Hillage, J. & Pollard, E.** (1998). Employability: developing a framework for policy analysis.
- **Almeida, R. & Leite Corseuil, C. H., & Poole, J.** (2018). The impact of digital technologies on worker tasks: Do labor policies matter?.
- **Autor, D. H. & Levy, F. & Murnane, R. J.** (2003). The skill content of recent technological change: An empirical exploration. *The Quarterly journal of economics*, 118(4), 1279-1333.
- **Acemoglu, D. & Autor, D.** (2011). Skills, tasks and technologies: Implications for employment and earnings. In *Handbook of labor economics* (Vol. 4, pp. 1043-1171). Elsevier.

- **Graetz, G.** & Michaels, G. (2015), 'Robots at Work', CEPS Discussion Paper 1335, London: London School of Economics, <http://cep.lse.ac.uk/pubs/download/dp1335.pdf>.
- **Goos, M.** & Manning, A. (2007). Lousy and lovely jobs: The rising polarization of work in Britain. *The review of economics and statistics*, 89(1), 118-133.
- **Ramírez-Montoya, M. S.** & Castillo-Martínez, I. M. & Sanabria-Z, J. & Miranda, J. (2022). Complex thinking in the framework of Education 4.0 and Open Innovation—A systematic literature review. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 8(1), 4.
- **Bonfils, P.** (2015). Immersion and digital environments: a methodological approach based on lived experience. *Communications issues*, (27), 261-277.
- **Petruzzello, G.** & Mariani, M. G. & Guglielmi, D. & Van Der Heijden, B. I. & de Jong, J. P., & Chiesa, R. (2023). The role of teaching staff in fostering perceived employability of university students. *Studies in Higher Education*, 48(1), 20-36.
- **González-Pérez, L. I.** & Ramírez-Montoya, M. S. (2022). Components of Education 4.0 in 21st century skills frameworks: systematic review. *Sustainability*, 14(3), 1493.